

The impact of Living Labs on mobility behaviour of active mobility users in East African context

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Abstract

Walking and cycling are the most prevalent modes of transport in Africa, with over a billion people relying on them daily. Yet poor-quality infrastructure continues to push many toward motorized transport. Before investing in costly, long-term projects, living labs offer a low-cost, flexible, and community-driven way to test and improve street design. Using a bottom-up approach, living labs empower communities to reimagine streets as inclusive, people-centered spaces.

This paper examines the impact of living labs on pedestrian and cyclist behavior in Mekelle, Ethiopia. The key mobility challenges were unsafe crossings, poor accessibility, narrow pedestrian spaces, and no cycling lanes. The living lab design was based on inputs from surveys and stakeholder engagements. The interventions included zebra crossing, widened walkways, bike lanes, greenery, and designated street vendor space. To assess its impact, surveys and drone imagery were collected before, during, and after implementation. Using YOLOv11, we created a dataset to analyse mobility patterns and users' behavior. The preliminary results showed most participants had never experienced a living lab before. The intervention was perceived as positive, improved pedestrian, cyclist, women and children's volumes. Since safety, accessibility and market activity were improved the respondents suggested more car-free zones in the city.

Key words

Walking, Cycling, Africa, Living Labs/ real-life experiments, Ethiopia

Introduction

Walking and cycling are the simplest and most universal forms of transport, increasingly recognized for their role in creating sustainable, healthy, and inclusive cities. These modes are highly space-efficient, accommodating more users while requiring minimal infrastructure (Gerike et al., 2021). In Africa, over a billion people rely on walking and cycling daily (UN-HABITAT, 2022). However, inadequate and poor-quality infrastructure continues to push many toward motorized transport. Despite being the most cost-effective option, active mobility remains largely overlooked in transport planning and funding.

This paper explores the impact of living labs on mobility behaviour and on improving walking and cycling environments in the context of African cities. Living labs are innovative, low-cost, temporary, and flexible interventions that adopt a bottom-up design approach and promote a "learning by doing" (Bertolini, 2020, Kinigadner et al., 2024a). They empower communities to reimagine and transform streets into inclusive, people-centred spaces.

A living lab experiment was implemented in October 2024 for three weeks on a selected street called 'Bitsuan street' in Mekelle, Ethiopia's second-largest city. The transport system in the city includes both motorized and non-motorized modes, with a modal share of two-thirds and one-third, respectively (Tewelde, 2018). The study aims to bridge the gap between pedestrians' and cyclists' perceptions and urban design practices by addressing the question: What roles can living labs play in influencing mobility behaviour in East African cities?

To assess this, the research will explore four guiding questions: (1) How can subjective perceptual qualities of streetscapes inform living labs design guidelines? (2) What role do living labs play in influencing users' behaviour in East Africa? (3) How do living labs affect the daily experiences of active mobility users?

The study uses a structured survey focusing on user perceptions before, during, and after living labs implementation, assessing the effectiveness and impact of these interventions. This approach helps identify key subjective qualities of streetscapes influencing active mobility. In addition, expert interviews, focus group discussions, and workshops will provide supporting qualitative data. Crowd mapping tools will also be used to audit walkability, bikability, and infrastructure quality on selected streets.

Literature review

Living labs and their impact on mobility behavior

Living labs are becoming more common tools to instrument the feasibility of long-term projects. Living labs are temporary interventions to raise awareness on how street space is utilized. Such interventions could be implemented using moveable, low-cost materials before changes in urban space become permanent (Hardinghaus & Weschke, 2023). Living labs is a particular type of pilot project changing the use, regulation, design, or function of street sections, entire streets, or even larger areas for a limited period of time (Bertolini, 2020). The most common items utilized in living labs include planters, benches, paint, and speed reduction measures. They are cheap, flexible/adjustable and can be implemented very fast. These street experiments can strongly promote active mobility by enabling a modal shift from cars to more sustainable modes (walking, cycling and public transport), improve safety, enhance social interaction, and have positive impacts on local businesses.

Living labs in Africa

While living labs are very common in different cities in the Global North, the concept of innovative living labs has received limited scholarly attention in the Global South (Andres et al., 2021a) with only a few creative living labs trends from the Global North that are sometimes imposed on the Global South. As Andres (2021) stress, “it is timely to consider what type of planning combined with localized and contextualized place-making is required for African cities that have different histories, lifestyles, environments, and planning systems (Andres et al., 2021b).

Despite these few promising practices, there is little to no impact assessment of the living labs on the mobility behavior of users and how these experiments benefit the city and the public in general and particularly in Africa (Cardoso et al., 2021, Eyler et al., 2015). Impact assessments of living labs can help to examine their effectiveness on mobility behavior and safety. Different impact types include perceptions, impacts on society, transport, economy, and environment (Kinigadner et al., 2024b, VanHoose et al., 2022) can be assessed. Considering Perceptions before, during, and after implementation can give insights into acceptance or attitudinal change (Kinigadner et al., 2024c).

Theoretical framework on mobility behavior

The relationship between attitude and behavior has been conceptualized by various theoretical frameworks, the most prominent one being the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991). This theory provides the basis for the theoretical framework for modal choice decisions, which are influenced by internal and social considerations, such as attitudes, norms, and habits. In this context, Mobility behavior refers to the subjective habits, attitudes and external sociocultural norms that influence individual's modal choice. Ajzen defines attitude as "the degree to which performance of the behavior is positively or negatively valued" and the subjective norm is the perceived social expectation to follow a certain behavior. Perceived behavioural control, on the other hand, is the individual's perception of the possibility of engaging or not engaging in a certain behavior.

Figure 1. Theoretical framework based on Ajzen's planned behavior adopted by the author.

In order to achieve goals such as increased bicycling and walking, understanding people's travel behavior is necessary since attitudes play an important role in travel decisions (Bhagat-Conway et al., 2024). Several Studies have investigated the impact of the attitude towards active travel (Fallah Zavareh et al., 2020) with a focus on walking (Lindelöw et al., 2014) or cycling (Fernández-Heredia et al., 2016). In this regard, Global South is extremely understudied in the travel behavior literature. Users' mobility behavior and modal choices in Sub-Saharan Africa depend on attitudes and perceptions, daily experiences, economic and social status of users. For some, car ownership is associated with status and wealth, leading to an increased preference for motorized transport among certain socioeconomic groups (Resnick, 2015). On the contrary, walking and cycling are

activities mainly undertaken by those with limited means of income and resources (Jones & Lucas, 2012).

Research methodology

Research approach

The study employed structured questionnaires that address sociodemographic factors, user perceptions, preferences, and daily experiences. This approach helped identify subjective qualities of streetscapes that significantly influence active mobility users' mobility behaviour. To evaluate the impact of the living labs, a mobility behavior survey was conducted with 90 participants at three stages: before, during, and after implementation. Drone imagery was also collected at each stage to complement the survey data. The drone imagery captured aerial views of the street throughout the intervention.

The other method was stakeholder engagement where multiple stakeholders from academia, NGO, government, and civil society have attended. Expert interviews and focus group discussions conducted during stakeholder engagement provided additional qualitative insights. Stakeholders were identified and mapped at the start of the project based on their influence and interest in sustainable mobility in general, and particularly in active mobility (walking and cycling), as shown in Figure 2. Stakeholder engagement activities included project briefings, workshops (more than five), site visits, and expert interviews (n=22). Most of the stakeholders listed in Figure 2 participated in the workshops and shared their perspectives and needs.

A crowd-mapping tool was also used to assess walkability, bikeability, and the quality of infrastructure along the selected case street (Bitsuan Street). After collecting data on the available street amenities along Bitsuan Street, as well as the major obstacles and challenges to walking and cycling, the information was analysed. Three core problems were identified: difficulties in crossing, limited pedestrian space, and the absence of cycling lanes. Based on these findings, we proposed solutions such as zebra crossings for safer movement, expanded and widened sidewalks, designated spaces for street vendors, dedicated bike lanes, and the addition of greenery or temporary plants.

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Figure 2. Stakeholder mapping

During the experts' workshops, stakeholders were asked to provide suggestions and design recommendations for creating inclusive and safe walkways and bicycle lanes as shown in Figure 3. Most of their recommendations were incorporated into the final living lab implementation.

Figure 3. Users identifying key problems and making suggestions on the living labs design in the workshop

Living labs urban design

The major mobility challenges identified by users and stakeholders were unsafe crossings, poor accessibility, limited pedestrian space, and absence of cycling lanes. The living lab design was based on these findings and through continuous stakeholder engagements. The intervention included solutions such as zebra crossings for safer movement, expanded pedestrian areas, designated spaces for street vendors, dedicated bike lanes, and greenery to enhance the walking and cycling environment.

Figure 4. Living labs urban design and implementation, Source: Simret H/Yesus

Analysis method

For the drone imagery, we start by capturing aerial images of the street before and after the living lab intervention. For the machine to be able to detect people we need a training library. As there is no available open-source library for aerial images in this context, we decided to build our own training library by manually annotating people using Roboflow. Once the library is finished, we use it to train the machine using different models. The initial training on Roboflow's free version (version 3.0) yielded a 65% accuracy, which was not satisfactory. Using the YOLO NAS model boosts the accuracy to 85% which is far better but still the error is not marginal. Consequently, we switched to using Python and YOLO11 on our local machine to improve the model's performance. The final model is designed to track people in both scenarios for further behavioural and traffic analysis. For example, quantitative analysis of people crossing the street using zebra crossing or not; people density diagrams categorized for each dedicated zone etc.

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Figure 5. Analysis method

Preliminary results

1. Survey results

Awareness about living labs

The findings show that 98% of respondents had never experienced a living lab intervention prior to this project. This highlights the novelty of the approach in the local context and suggests a significant gap in exposure to participatory, community-driven urban design interventions. The lack of prior experience also emphasizes the importance of such experiments in raising awareness and introducing alternative, people-centered approaches to street design.

Figure 6. Users' awareness before and after the implementation of the living lab, n=90, in %

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Before the implementation of the living lab

After the implementation of the living lab

Figure 7. Bitsuan street before and after the implementation of the living lab, Source: the author

Effectiveness of the living labs

After implementation, the impact on active mobility was rated as positive by 74% and very positive by 22% of respondents, while 84% found the intervention effective in creating safe and accessible pedestrian space. According to the respondents, key changes included: increased pedestrian volume, reduced congestion, improved market activity, and lower theft rates.

Figure 8. effectiveness of the implemented living-labs, n=90, in %

Expected impact

Nearly all respondents (98%) supported expanding the intervention and introducing more car-free zones in the city, noting that it created safer and more pleasant walking environments. They also expressed interest in seeing more positive impacts on the

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mobility behavior of active mobility users and emphasized the need for better street design in the future.

Figure 4. Respondents answer to the question 'In which aspect would you expect an impact? n=90, in %

Recommended interventions

The main recommended Living Lab interventions are the installation of zebra crossings and the widening of sidewalks, as illustrated in the figure.

Figure 10. recommended living lab interventions to be expanded, n=90, in %

2. Drone imagery results

The drone imagery is still being annotated and analysed; however, some noticeable changes have already been observed. These include increased pedestrian volumes, reduced congestion, improved market activity, and more effective use of sidewalks and zebra crossings. The living labs demonstrated how simple and innovative interventions can reshape streets to better serve the majority while also reducing infrastructure costs. Moreover, they helped raise awareness by positioning walking as a key priority on the urban agenda. Once the analysis is finalized, findings will include pedestrians' cumulative dwelling time, the exact volumes of pedestrians and cyclists, gap acceptance, mobility patterns, and the use of interventions (sidewalks, zebra crossings, and cycling lanes) before and after implementation.

Annotated image before the living lab

Annotated image after the living lab

Annotated image after the living lab

Figure 11. Annotated images from the drone imagery before and after the implementation of the living lab

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